

INVOLVEMENTS IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE SERVICES: A CLOSE ENCOUNTER WITH HOME ECONOMICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. This study viewed the close encounter with food and beverages services of home economics teachers specifically in Baguio district, Davao City. There were eight (8) home economics teachers who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the HE teachers in the school. The in-depth-interview was employed to gather some information as regards to their respective experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as it relates to the involvements of the participants: the experiences of the working students were on their difficulty balancing work and school duties, economically underprivileged and aiming to finish studies. The coping mechanisms of the working students were: Managing time wisely, focusing on the current duties and staying healthy and energetic. The educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study were: Engage working students in flexible learning mode, Provide proper guidance and school support to working students and Encourage peer learning. The home economics teachers may be more receptive to the need of their students. Other considerations for working students may be crafted to give enough time and space for them. The teachers may be more sensitive to the needs and wants of their students. The students may be directed well by their classroom advisers and the guidance counsellor of the school. The teacher's attention to each of the students in the classroom plays a significant value specifically to the working students that they may be given proper guidance and directions for them to complete their dreamed diploma and gain a better life in the future.

KEY WORDS

1. Close encounter
2. food and beverages services
3. home economics teachers

1. Introduction

Teaching home economics is one of the most exciting disciplines in the academe. This area involves several areas of varying characteristics. One of the most challenging tasks in this area is how to transfer the skills to the learners. It cannot be denied that each learner is equipped with different skills and expertise, thus, the challenge begins when the class starts to lay down all its activities particularly in the line of food and beverages services. Rai (2023) elucidated that those in the food and beverage industry have an obligation to serve safe, properly packaged, and fresh items to consumers. The food and beverage department holds the responsibil-

ity for maintaining high standards of food and service, costing of the food, and maintenance of bar and restaurant. With fast-changing customer demands and strict health regulations, the importance of the handling processes for food and beverage plays a vital role. Food beverage handling is important because unsafe food may lead to foodborne illness or food poisoning in the consumers. A WHO report suggests that foodborne illnesses may cause long-lasting disability and even death. World Health Organization (2010) reported that food and beverage marketing has been identified as one factor driving the upward trend in global obesity rates among children. Indeed, an extensive body of research has shown that children's exposure to this marketing, much of which promotes food and beverages of low nutritional quality, influences their dietary preferences, purchasing behaviors, and consumption patterns. Based on this evidence, the World Health Organization has urged countries to develop policies to protect children from the marketing of unhealthy food and beverages. Doumeizel, V (2019) revealed that an estimated 600 million people, almost 1 in 10 people in the world, fall ill as a result of eating contaminated food and 420,000 die every year. In 2004, 160 countries voted at the United Nations to make food – safe food – a human right rather than a commodity, but risks to safety continue with many challenges putting strains on supply chains. The world is in the midst of a nutritional transition, facing over-nutrition in some regions and under-nutrition in others. With the global population expected to exceed nine billion by 2050, pressures have been placed on existing food systems and this has implications for food safety. Foodborne illnesses, from E. coli to listeria, threaten lives and everyone – consumers, companies and governments has an important role to play in improving the status quo. Social Tables (2021) conveyed that as budgets continue to shrink and the cost of food continues to rise, it's easy to look at food service at events as a have to do." You might be tempted to scrape something together for the lowest dollar amount. But that rarely pays off. And that's because food and beverage at events isn't just about keeping people full" it's a part of the experience. If serving food at events was really just about feeding people, it would probably be more cost effective to give guests cash or vouchers to the nearest fast-food restaurant. There's a reason events fall into the greater hospitality industry. The event organizer" whether it's a corporation, an association, or an individual" is the host of an event. The attendees are the host's guests. The idea of hospitality goes back to biblical times, when people would open their homes to guests" even strangers" and break bread. The idea of sharing a meal led to shared conversations, shared ideas, shared fellowship. Biscotti, L. (2023) narrated that while inflation is often helping nudge revenues upward, managing margins may be the biggest challenge and the biggest story for many FB companies today. Amid inflation, rising interest rates and growing labor costs, maintaining margins can be challenging. Carrefour, for instance, has identified growing margins as a priority. In the battle to restore and grow margins, businesses are reducing waste, increasing private label, shifting sourcing and, of course, raising prices so that margins stay healthy – or get bigger. The proof, as the saying goes, is in the pudding, but when it comes to profits, it may be in the margins. Nestlé CEO Mark Schneider at the end of 2022 said, "margins continued to be resilient," but added that 2023 would bring "a focus on restoring our gross margin." Growing margins isn't magic, but there are strategies and steps you can take to boost margins and grow profits, even if that doesn't always mean growing sales. Although inflation is hitting nearly everything, FB companies are seeing inflation's impact due to the cost of materials. Carrefour said margins were impacted by increases in costs for services, energy, and materials such as paper. "Pricing, growth leverage

and efficiencies “helped to partly offset the impact of cost inflation, according to Nestlé, which added that administrative expenses as a percentage of sales benefited from “disciplined cost control.” Reducing waste and tightening costs can boost margins. The school environment can enhance children’s skills, knowledge and behaviours in relation to healthy eating. However, in many countries, unhealthy foods are commonly available in schools, and children can be exposed to aggressive marketing by the food industry. The Department of Education’s policy ‘Orders’ represented a relatively strong policy framework for the education sector of the Philippines. However, a lack of human and financial resources for implementation, planning, and policy enforcement limited the impact of the policy on the healthiness of school food provision. Ambiguity in policy wording allowed a wide interpretation of the foods eligible to be provided in schools, and led to difficulties in effective monitoring and enforcement. Food companies used existing relationships with schools to promote their brands and compromise the establishment of a stronger food policy agenda (Reeve et al (2018). Philippine Food and Beverage Alliance (2017) reported that there are over 46,000 schools in the Philippines, providing kindergarten to Grade 12 education. In many densely-populated areas classes are delivered across two sessions per day, with sessions starting from 6 am and closing up to 6 pm. Education as a sector is centralized and organized by central, regional and divisional policy layers, with health and nutrition officer functions framed as a ‘learner support’ services. Department of Education Orders “Dep Ed Orders” are the overarching policy framework governing the rights, obligations and operations of the school setting, including the provision, marketing and sale of food. While the country is currently without a national regulatory mandate to protect children from harmful marketing of unhealthy foods and beverages there is an industry-initiated self-regulated pledge called the Responsible Advertising to Children Initiative (the ‘Philippines Pledge’). In the local scenario, particularly in Baguio District, Davao City, it has been clearly noticed that the students in the secondary level, has been exposed to a lot of laboratory activities specifically in food and beverages services. However, I have notices that some of the students in the class were hesitant in performing their tasks in the course. As a result of this, the home economics teacher is dutybound to provide the best lessons pertaining to food and beverages (F and B) services. This idea has also led most of the teachers in quandary as to how these challenges or problems be given a quick solution. At this point, as a home economics teacher handling F and B courses , I know very well the ways and means in dealing with such local problems that we have, however, I also need to determine other teachers predicaments pertaining to these existing issues in our district, particularly in our school.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the narratives of the home economics teachers as they had their close encounters with their students in the food and beverage classes. This research also dealt with the coping mechanisms of the home economics teachers. The teachers’ insights about their respective experiences in dealing with these students were also noted.

- (1) What are involvements of HE teachers in Teaching food and beverages Services?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of HE teachers in dealing with the challenges of teaching F and B services?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.2. Theoretical Lens—

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

This study was anchored on Technical Education and Skills Development Act of 1994 (Republic Act No. 7796) Section 22, “Establishment and Administration of the National Trade Skills Standards” of RA 7796 known as the TESDA Act of 1994 mandates TESDA to establish national occupational skill standards. The Authority shall develop and implement a certification and accreditation program in which private industry groups and trade associations are accredited to conduct approved trade tests, and the local government units to promote such trade testing activities in their respective areas in accordance with the guidelines to be set by the Authority. The FOOD AND BEVERAGE SERVICES NC II Qualification consists of competencies that a person must achieve to provide food and beverage service to guests in various food and beverage service facilities. This study was further anchored to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), behaviors are influenced by intentions, which are determined by

three factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) predicts that planned behaviors are determined by behavioral intentions which are largely influenced by an individual’s attitude toward a behavior, the subjective norms encasing the execution of the behavior, and the individual’s perception of their control over the behavior. Ajzen (1991) proposed the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) wherein the individual’s behavior is best predicted by one’s intentions; intentions are, in turn, predicted by attitudes about the behavior, the subjective norms (a person’s perception of important others’ beliefs that he or she should or should not perform the behavior) encasing the execution of the behavior, and the individual’s perception of their control over the behavior. Ajzen’s TPB has been used to predict many different behaviors ranging from gambling behaviors to the use of hormone replacement therapy.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal

histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg. This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions—T*

he philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model for example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigms a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities on the experiences of home economics teachers as they taught food and beverage services to their students were accounted and interpreted by the researcher. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different

perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The purpose of this research was to gather important details on the experiences and coping mechanisms of the participants of the study, all of whom were home economics teachers who were handling the same course particularly those coming from Baguio District,

Davao City. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the experiences and challenges of the home economics teachers who were handling courses in F and B services. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining the experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms of the participants of this study.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the experiences and challenges of the home economics teachers were unleashed based on their personal narratives about their close encounters with their students. The researcher’s drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the close encounters of the home economics teachers became the basis for doing a qualitative research,

a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morris-

sey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by

analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher anticipated that the subjective experiences and challenges of the home economics teachers were drawn from the personal encounters of the teachers with their students particularly during their class hours in teaching food and beverage services to their respective students.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this pro-

cess the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013)

2.4. Research Participants—The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the home economics teachers who had close encounters with their students during laboratory hours. The participants must have at least three (3) years of teaching food and beverage services in their respective schools. Regardless of their sex, age and marital status, the participants were considered to take part in this study. Additionally, all the participants were coming from the secondary level. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size the quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or

all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to

gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves

determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the home economics teachers from, Baguio district, Davao City. Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The selected home economics teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting informa-

2.6. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began

tion involved primarily in the Virtual In Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data; Davidson’s (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies.

The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the videocall via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants. The participants also filled-in the Interview Form provided to them and submit the same to the researcher.

with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She

then finds statements about how individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called “meaning units” or themes. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This was called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it’s a flexible method which can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination,

and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

2.7. *Analytical Framework*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group

consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their

frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words.

I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as develop by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful tome in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

Fig. 2. Framework of the Study

The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, (Ritchie Spencer, as cited by Goldsmith, 2021). includes an analysis of the important qualities These concepts, technologies, and associations depicted in the charts. This analysis should mirror the participant. Therefore, any strategies or recommendations the researcher offers be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in reflect the participants’ real views, beliefs, and interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies of developing the study’s analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions and its answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The participants unraveled their experiences as they revealed their views on their experiences in teaching food and beverage in Baguio district, Davao City.

3.0.1. What are involvements of HE teachers in Teaching food and beverages Services?— The home economics teachers had been deeply immersed in teaching food and beverage in their respective classes. The involvements of the teachers were rooted from their basic knowledge in home economics. It was only recently that various strands in home economics were identified. There were different areas to choose from, however, the school’s specialty was on F and B.

*3.0.2. Enhancing students Critical thinking skills. —*One of the most important tasks of home economics teachers is to enhance the critical thinking skills of the students. Despite the fact that this course deals with hands on food preparations, still, critical thinking abilities plays an important role in the success of the activity. Without critical thinking processes, the outcomes of the food preparations of the students would not be great and appreciated.

Fig. 3. Involvements of HE teachers in Teaching food and beverages Services

3.0.3. Developing Project management skills—Being in the home economics laboratory does not mean only cooking and food preparations. It entails the idea of project management skills to make the event more successful. Without project management, the expected outcomes of the class activities would not be successful. As time passes by in the F and B class, the students gradually develop their skills in managing their class activities.

3.0.4. Enhancing Creativity—As always thought of, home economics is not totally an idea of ladle and frying pan, the F and B processes requires creativity. The more creative the students in their class activities, the better would be their presentation and the palatability of their prepared food is exceptional. The more creative the students, the better were their outputs and presentations.

3.1. Coping mechanisms of HE teachers in dealing with the challenges of teaching F and B services.—

3.1.1. Conducting mini tour—It is always a fact the home economics teachers encounter various problems in their classes. Teaching food and beverage is not easy and demands a great amount of energy and planning to implement the class activities. Problems pertaining to the availability or presence of food establishments in the nearby areas were inevitable. Some activities were not realistic and cannot be performed in the classroom and the lack of communication among the members of the group is another factor to deal with in the classroom.

3.1.2. Finding ways to perform the activities—Performing class activities in F and B course was not easy. There were times when some of the main components of the food or menu was not available. There were also times that the cooking wares were not usable and the

Fig. 4. Coping mechanisms of HE teachers in dealing with the challenges of teaching F and B services
 worst was that, there were not available.

3.1.3. *Communicating updates with students*—Communication with all the students in the class was essential in the conduct of the classes in food and beverage sections. Without proper discussions of the procedures and materials needed to perform the tasks. it was also very important that the students get the latest updates of their class activities.

3.2. *Educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study*—The insights gained from the narratives of the home economics teacher participants were worth keeping for the improvement of the teaching and learning of home economics as a course. Understanding the millennials characteristics plays an important role of their survival in this very demanding times.

3.2.1. *Constantly monitoring students' performance tasks*—One of the techniques in holding a successful home economics class was to constantly monitor the different class performance of the students. There should be a regular monitoring of student's performance and provide the students with the feedbacks bases on their actual class tasks.

3.2.2. *Instilling food safety procedures*—Food and safety protocols plays a vital role in the food preparations. Proper food safety handling is important in making better food and satisfy the cravings of other people. The safer the food for the consumers, the better would be the health of the consumers. Instilling the idea of food safety in a regular basis makes a healthier community.

Fig. 5. Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to explore the views of home economics teachers in their respective classes in food and beverage, specifically in Baguio District, Davao City. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Creswell’s (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of the teacher’s experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own ideas on the phenomenon being explored which were the experiences of home economics teachers in teaching Food and Beverage (F and B) in the secondary level.

4.1. *Findings*—Based on the results of thematic analysis of the responses of the home economics teacher participants as to their experiences, coping and insights about their teaching F and B in their classes. The involvements of home economics teachers were: Enhancing students Critical thinking skills, Developing Project management skills and Enhancing students performance tasks and Instilling food safety procedures

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The involvement of home economics teachers in their class activities revolve around their prepared yearlong prepared laboratory lessons. It can be said that most of the teachers in home economics were very much familiar with the peculiarities of each of their class activities. They knew which activity would be done easiest and which one requires innovations or adjustments in the preparation. The involvements of Home Economics (HE) were complex in the sense that each activity, particularly in food and beverage area demands so much time, effort and the ingredients that needs to be at hand prior to the conduct of the activity. These activities do not only require the aforementioned steps, but above all, these needs the inclusion of critical thinking skills. The students need such skill to think about the procedures, doing and performing procedures based on the required steps to come up with the expected results. Do-

ing food and beverage processes requires more than action, it needs the brain working fully to attain the outcomes of the activity. Another involvement of the HE teachers were the development of project management skills of the students. One of the most crucial skills of the people involved in Food and Beverage (FB) is the success of their affair. The students should be made aware that their food preparations is not intended for one or two people, there are times when they had to think about the number of guests coming in for the occasion, the quantity and quality of food and beverage they had to prepare, the venue and other important party requirements. This is a huge event that requires project management skills. This means, the event must be well planned way ahead of time. The third involvement of HE teachers were on enhancing the creativity of the students. Setting aside the actual procedures in F and B, the student's creativity is another factor for the success of these students. It is not enough to just prepare the food, cook it and process it. The F and B presentation is a very significant factor that enhances the food and taste of the banquet. The need to enhance the student's creativity should also be at the forefront of the learning processes of each of the students taking the course. There were many challenges encountered during the F and B preparations and procedures. There were many activities that cannot be done totally in the schools' premises, there were times when the teachers need to take the students in the nearby food and beverage establishments to actually see the real scenario of their course topic. Conducting mini-tour in nearby coffee shops, snack house or bars made the process easier and faster. The students need to see the actual scenario of their lessons, thus, taking them outside the school laboratory was much quicker and realistic. Most of the time, the F and B preparations may lack ingredients for the preparation, sometimes, the needed instruments or materials were not available. These problems do not hinder the teachers and students in performing their activities. Often, the teacher's guide the students on how to perform the procedures faster and easier. These procedures depend so much on the set-up of the laboratory and creativity of all the members of the group. Another identified themes on the coping mechanisms of the HE teachers was communicating updates with the students. Nowadays, it is important the teachers are more aware of the rapid changes and innovations in the F and B industry. The teachers have to keep themselves on dated with the recent developments in the F and B industry and these has to be communicated with the students for them to be aware of these latest trends in the industry. The insights drawn from the HE teachers revealed two significant factors. The first one is on the constant monitoring student's performance tasks. As teachers, they may device some ways in monitoring their students' activities, specifically in F and B. Pictures or videos may be submitted to the teachers for marking their individual or group performance. At this time, it is much easier to monitor the activities of the students despite their physical absence in the class. Most of the technologies such as cellular phones, videos and in still pictures taken during their activities were significant in assessing the students' performance. Another insight drawn from the responses of the participants was on instilling food safety practices. In the F and B industry, it is important to keep in mind the principles of food safety. Whatever F and B were prepared, it must serve the consumers with utmost safety that they will enjoy be satisfied. The food preparation matters so much in this industry. The consumers health and well being are the prime consideration of this industry. Therefore, it is important the food and beverage served to the people will benefit them.

4.3. *Future Directions—*

Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The findings of the study as to the involvement of home economics teachers in F and B as well as their coping mechanisms and insights may provide a great information to the following entities: The DepEd Personnel and School Heads may revisit the site or laboratories of home economics in the schools under their supervision to ensure that the expected outcomes of the course were delivered and that the materials needed for the students performance tasks are available. The home economics teachers may improve their innovativeness in the preparation of the F and B activities. The teachers may attend seminars that would enhance their teaching skills in home economics courses. The parents may be guided by the teachers through constant meetings to unravel the learning difficulties of their children and help them reach their goals in educating their children and make them more independent and responsible home member. The students may be given their own daily routine responsibilities in their house food preparations. The home economics learners may be guided properly to enrich their knowledge in home economics, specifically in Food and Beverage, that this course is not only intended to improve their skills in cooking but being more knowledgeable on how to live and be healthy. For the future researchers, a similar study may be conducted in other regions or divisions. The researchers may consider other stakeholders as participants. This research may also be shared to other researchers through research conventions, colloquia and publications.

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